

The Parish of Kilmichael Glassary in the late seventeenth century

Alexander Donald Stewart
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Figure 1. Map of Argyll and adjacent counties as far east as Glasgow, based on Arrowsmith's Map of Scotland (1807). Argyll is tinted dark grey. The parish of Kilmichael Glassary is delimited by dots.

The following essay is an attempt to reconstruct the social and economic condition of Glassary parish during the late seventeenth century, relying mainly on the sources transcribed in the appendices. However, the attempt requires a glance at Scottish history, for the period in question was marked by civil war, fear and uncertainty.

Historical background

The fierce discontent with the Roman church in the Lowlands of Scotland, persuaded the parliament to legislate in 1560 to disestablish the Roman Catholic church and substituted the new Protestant faith as the national religion. The population of the Scottish Highlands, including Argyll, hitherto firmly Roman Catholic, suddenly found itself nominally Protestant. Many resented this, including sections of the nobility and even the royal family. The result was intermittent civil war.

The war eventually reached Argyll. In 1644 Alexander McDonald was sent from Ireland with a Catholic army to assist Royalist forces in Scotland, fighting the Protestant Covenanters, i.e., the government army. But in 1645 MacDonald decided to withdraw his forces and use them to burning and pillaging Argyll. This was basically a clan feud, for Argyll had been MacDonald land before it was granted to the Campbells. The destruction and famine caused by McDonald's army in Argyll over the years 1645 to 1647 has been amply documented by McKerral (1948, pp. 42–48).

In 1647 the Scottish parliament decided to crush McDonald, sending to Argyll two Highland regiments and six troops of horse commanded by Lt. General David Leslie. However, the soldiers brought with them typhus. In consequence, Argyll, already visited by famine, was decimated by disease. Roughly half the farms in southern Kintyre were abandoned (McKerral 1948, p. 78). Glassary fared better. Only 15% of the surnames in 1670 are of lowland origin (Appendix I), a percentage assumed to indicated the number of tenancies liberated as a result of the epidemic, and then taken up by Lowland families. It will be noted that as late as 1692 some farms were still unoccupied (Appendix VIII).

Not long after the 1647 the tide of war turned yet again. This time the Protestant Lowlanders, the so-called Covenanters, were the object of attack by the forces of King Charles II. The persecution lasted from 1666 until 1685, inspiring many Protestant Lowlanders to leave the counties of Renfrew and Ayr to join relations in Argyll. The number of separate Lowland surnames in Campbeltown doubled between 1665 and 1685 (McKerral 1948, p. 119). A similar increase is evident in Glassary (Appendix I).

Argyll was last convulsed by strife in 1685, when Archibald, Earl of Argyll (1629–1685) called upon his 'vassals', all nominally Protestants, to join him in a badly planned attempt to overthrow the Roman Catholic king of Scotland, James II & VII. However, either due to caution or conviction, only a third of the men of Glassary enlisted (Mactavish 1935, pp. 7–8). This was fortunate, for the rebellion

was soon crushed and 105 rebels from Glassary had their livestock, mainly cows, forfeited in October the same year (Appendix V). The Earl of Argyll was captured, tried and executed.

The Scottish parliament in 1690, recognizing the importance of an efficient national army, decided to finance it through a hearth tax. The following year, 1691, a proclamation called to arms all men between the ages of 16 and 60 years, 'for putting the countrey in a posture of Defence against an Invasion of French and Irish Papists'. The lists of those who paid the hearth tax and those who were called to arms are given in Appendices VII and VIII. Note that half the men recruited were armed already.

Land ownership—the heritors

Of the 33 Glassary landowners, or heritors, Campbells were by far the most important, owning 65% of the parish by value in 1688 (Appendix VI). Even the parish ministers were Campbells, for until 1692 it was the heritors who selected them.

The lands were not freehold, but granted as feus, or leases. These feus were in some cases held directly from the Crown, but more commonly from a feudal superior. In return there were obligations of fealty together with an annual tax, or feu-duty. A feu could be inherited or sold, or even terminated if fealty was in doubt. The feus listed in the 1688 valuation as 'pertaining to his Majesty' are an example. They were extinguished because their owners had supported the Earl of Argyll's attempt to overthrow the King. A comparison of the list of heritors in 1688 (Appendix VI) with the hearth tax roll of 1691 (Appendix VII) and the valuation of 1750 (Appendix X) shows numerous other changes of ownership, mostly sales due to bankruptcy.

The most prominent Glassary families in 1688 were Campbell of Auchinbreck and Campbell of Silvercraigs who had, between them, 36% of the whole parish by value. Two other prominent heritors were the Laird of MacLauchlan and Lamont of Monydrean. Most of the heritors, however, owned but one or two farms. The locations of the heritors' residences are shown in Fig. 3.

Campbell of Auchinbreck

The principal Glassary heritor in 1688 was Campbell of Auchinbreck, a branch of the Argyll family (Tweed 1871, pp. 179–184).

The reason for Auchinbreck's lands being listed in Appendix 4 as 'now pertaining to the King' is that Sir Duncan Campbell (†1700) was one of those unwise enough to side with the Earl of Argyll in his unsuccessful attempt to overthrow the King in 1685. Until then he had resided comfortably in Carnasserie Castle, close to Kilmartin in the adjacent parish of that name, with his family and servants, entertained by his harpist Duncan McIndeor (Sanger & Kinnaird 2016, pp. 119–120). Auchinbreck's lands were consequently forfeited, although he got them back in 1687 when the king made an attempt to establish freedom of religion in his

kingdom with the Declaration of Indulgence. Carnassarie Castle, however, had in the meantime been burnt down. He moved his seat in 1690 to Kinlochgair (now Lochgair), on Lochfyneside (Smith 1845, p. 694; see Fig. 3). There is, however, no trace of the house in the 1691 hearth tax roll (Appendix VII).

Campbell of Kilmory

A scion of the Auchinbreck family were heritors of the large Kilmory estate in Glassary from 1515 (Fig. 3). This estate was diminished by one half in 1700:

February 9 1704—Minute of agreement, dated at Inveraray 6 August 1700, between Mr. Dugall Campbell of Kilmory and Mr. Daniel Campbell, minister at Kilmichael in Glassary, whereby the former promises to dispose to the latter irredeemably the three merkland of Uila [Uillian] with the fishings and pertinents in the parish of Glassary, for which the minister is to pay 2200 merks [£1467 Scots]...(Paton 1913, p. 50).

The date of the sale, 1700, is significant, for it corresponds to the collapse of the Darien scheme. This ambitious Scottish project has been described as ‘the most disastrous speculation on record; established by act of the Scottish parliament, and begun by unprecedented excitement’ (MacLean 1900, p. 75). It aimed at great wealth by colonising part of the isthmus of Panama, and attracted investments from the wealthy and the wise. Its collapse wiped out some 20% of the money in circulation in Scotland. None of the Glassary heritors subscribed to the scheme, however so this was not directly responsible for the sale of Uillian (MacLean 1900, pp. 80–87). The money from the sale was probably intended for John Campbell, the brother of Dugald Campbell of Kilmory.

John Campbell, an army officer, was involved in the Darien scheme as commander of the troops sent to protect the settlers. But after the scheme collapsed in 1700 he settled in Jamaica, where he married the heiress of an American plantation owner. John Campbell started acquiring land in 1706, firstly at Black River in the Jamaican parish of St. Elizabeth, but later in the adjacent parish of Westmoreland. From the data bank formed by the Centre for the study of the legacies of British Slavery (UCL) and other sources, it appears that when he died in 1740 he owned plantations covering 3925 acres (nearly 16 square kilometres), and employed 460 slaves of both sexes, all engaged in the production of sugar, molasses and rum (RGD 1740). There was nothing unusual about this: Britain had had undisputed possession of Jamaica from the Treaty of Madrid in 1670 and, according to the National Library of Jamaica, by the time the British parliament passed the Slave Trade Abolition Act in 1807 an estimated 600,000 African slaves had been brought to work in the plantations for the settlers.

John Campbell advised his brother Dugald Campbell of Kilmory to send all his sons to Jamaica, together ‘with all the means with which he could furnish them’. Dugald took this advice so seriously that in addition to sending his sons James, John, Peter and Colin, he also recovered his daughter’s dowry from his son-in-law

and sent that (Campbell 1873, p. 81). The sale of Ullian, mentioned above, has to be seen in this context.

All Dugald's sons became plantation owners. So did John's own sons. John Campbell's epitaph in St. Elizabeth, which summarizes his life history, observes that 'he was the first Campbell who settled in this island and thro' his extream generosity and assistance, many are now possessed of opulent fortunes' (Lawrence Archer 1875, p. 340). The 'opulent fortunes' were no exaggeration, though none of the wealth came back to Glassary until 1816 when the last of the family, Peter Campbell, started rebuilding the family seat at Kilmory (Smith 1845, p. 687). It is doubtful if he spent much time there, though, for when he died in 1822 he was resident at No 27 Upper Montague Street in London (Campbell 1822).

Campbell of Silvercraigs

The estate of Silvercraigs was purchased by a wealthy merchant burges of Glasgow, Robert Campbell, about 1662. Robert was a son of Colin Campbell, provost of the city in 1636 (Stuart 1848, p. 99). The Silvercraigs estate had formerly belonged to a branch of the Lamont family. The Lamonts of Silvercraigs once had the 24 merkland of Duppín, Ballimore, Kilmichelbeg, Lingarton, Duncholgan, Achnaba, and Ardnaherrir, but lost it all in 1662 as a result of misfortune and debt (McKechnie 1938, p. 461–465). Silvercraigs, it may be noted, was not a farm, but a crag formed of silver-coloured rock on the coast of Loch Fyne, about 3 km south-east of Kilmory (Fig. 3).

MacLachlan of Stralachlan

The Laird of MacLachlan mentioned in the 1688 list of heritors (Appendix VI) was Archibald MacLachlan (1635–1687), 15th hereditary chief of the Clan MacLachlan. The principal MacLachlan lands were along the east side of Loch Fyne, opposite Glassary, centred on Old Castle Lachlan. The remains of the castle are to be seen about 8 km south-west of Strachur. As can be seen from the list of heritors in 1688 (Appendix VI), there were also other MacLachlan heritors in Glassary apart from the Laird.

Lamont

Like the MacLachlans, the Lamonts were a clan with lands mainly in Cowal, but also in Glassary. The long history of the Lamonts of Monydrain has been described in detail by McKechnie (1938, pp. 378–393). By 1688 they were in decline, holding Monydrain and Drum only, whereas they previously had Achahoish, Achnabreck and Fernoch.

Alexander Lamont of Monydraine was one of the few heritors certainly resident in Glassary in 1691. He lived in a house with one hearth (Appendix VII). It is recorded that when he died in 1699

After paying £43 of funeral expenses the moveable estate was but £83, to which a creditor was confirmed. Four cows at £13, 6s 8d a piece, two stirks at £3, 6s. 8d., a little bere in [the] barn at £5, 3s, eight sheep at 2 merks, and household plenishings and nets worth £6, 13s. 4d. made up the sorry total (McKechnie 1938, p. 387).

The wretched state of Alexander Lamont's finances underscores the divide between great and small heritors. Campbell of Auchinbreck, who had more land than merely his Glassary holdings, lived in a castle, whereas the smaller heritors mostly lived in conditions little better than their tenants. They even stooped to dishonesty to make ends meet, as shown by the appearance of John Campbell of Leckuary among the guilty in the delinquents list of 1709 (Appendix IX).

The farms

The land was divided into 55 large farms, cultivated by groups of resident families, in separate cottages;

the work of the farm is carried on in common among the whole tenants, with their wives and children. They seldom employ any servants...(Campbell 1793, vol. 8, p. 97).

This was the way the land was cultivated in 1793 and in earlier centuries. It is an unfamiliar practice today, but was intended to ensure that the workers needed to work the land were permanently available. A similar practice was common in parts of Italy until 60 years ago (Stewart 2015, pp. 32–45).

Since there were no accurate maps before the nineteenth century, the size of the farms and estates could only be quantified by means of the merkland valuations which had been established by the Scottish crown between 1222 and 1264. The valuation was based on the silver one mark coin then in use. Glassary comprised 238 merklands in 1688 (Appendix VI) and the population was about 1200, so each merkland supported about 5 people, roughly an average family. This accords with what was written a century later by Smith in his review of agriculture in Argyll;

in general, one merkland may give full employ to one plough and one family in the more arable parts of the country (Smith 1798, p. 31).

Another estimate of merkland valuation comes from a document of 1669 in which the Duke of Argyll granted Donald MacTavish the feu of Dunardry, a farm which borders Glassary to the south. The lands were valued at 7½ merks, and covered 526 hectares (1300 acres), of which 97 hectares (240 acres) were arable. From this we get an average merkland with 13 hectares of arable land and 57 hectares of rough grazing (Bradford 1991, p. 1).

The merkland valuations continued to be used into the eighteenth century, implying that the boundaries of the farms had remained the same for at least 500 years. This is corroborated by Timothy Pont's map of Glassary and Kilmartin, sketched between 1584 and 1596. The map records 75 farm names almost all of which are easily recognizable today (Stone 1989, pp. 99–100).

Figure 2. Graph of Glassary farm size in merklands, from Appendix X, against the number of resident families in 1691, from Appendix VII. The farms named were those whose inhabitants were not all engaged in agriculture. The number of farms is 55.

The 1750 valuation of Glassary (Appendix X) lists the assessed rental of each farm in merks and pounds sterling. There is no record of their size in acres, though this may sometimes be found from estate maps. It is clear, however, that they were all large and mostly suited to hill grazing. A typical example is the 5 merkland of Dunamuck, known from an estate map to have covered 804 acres (320 hectares) of which 70% was grazing, 26% was arable, and 3% plantations (Buchanan 1831). This farm in 1691 supported nine families, which does not, apparently, support the view that one merkland would support one family, as stated earlier. However, a graph of number of merklands against number of hearths suggests a reason.

The graph (Fig. 2) shows several farms with many more families than might be expected from the number of merklands. The most notable is Kilmichael, a 3 merkland with 14 families, rather than just three. Six other Glassary farms with 'excess' families were Dunamuck, Glasvar, Ederlinbeg, Duppin, Ballimore Aird and Kilmory. The explanation of these 'excess' families is that they were not all

directly cultivating the land. Kilmichael, far from being a farm, had become a village, as described later. Dunamuck had both a resident miller and a resident kiln-master, Glasvar, Ederlinbeg and Duppin all had a resident miller, and Ballimore had a resident kiln-master. Kilmory had both a kiln-master and the only carpenter in the parish. When these farms are left out of the graph the correlation between hearths and families holds quite well.

Fishing on Loch Fyne Another is another occupation which might have supported families but which would not have been suspected from the hearth tax.

The tenants

The majority of the population were subsistence farmers, tenants of the heritors. In most countries they would be called peasants. A glance at the 1691 list in Appendix VII, shows that of 228 householders, of whom only 5 were women, there were at least two heritors. There were four water-mills with full-time millers, at Dunamuck, Glasvar, Duppen and Ederlinbeg, one smith (at Kilmichael) and one carpenter (at Kilmory). There were also three men in charge of kilns, described in other documents as maltmen, i.e., whisky distillers. All the rest of the householders might be presumed to be farmers, but here is clear evidence that some were not. This is particularly evident at Kilmichael Glassary where there was a merchant:

17 July 1691—Bond by Donald Campbell, merchant in Kilmichael of Glassary, to George Herbertson, merchant in Glasgow, for £45-5s Scots, dated at Glasgow 19th September 1683 (Paton 1913, p. 4).

The same man signed another bond in 1683, this time to another merchant in Glasgow (Paton 1913, p. 15), and yet another in 1688 to a merchant in Inveraray (Paton 1913, p. 20). In 1696 a merchant in Kilmichael Glassary called Alexander Beetone appears in a bond (Paton 1913, p. 23).

Merchants sold mainly ironware, for example scythe blades, knives, chisels, horseshoes and bits, but also other items not easily made at home such as saddlery, tar, soap, candles and rope. A merchant in Campbeltown in 1672 offered an even wider selection of articles, including spices and silks (McKerral 1948, p. 132).

Kilmichael also had a smith, the only one in the parish, who may have employed at least a hammer-man. The village hosted annually two cattle markets, to which cattle from Knapdale and Islay were driven and sold to Lowland dealers. In the nineteenth century these markets took place in May and October (Pigot 1837, p. 230). The latter was no doubt the more important for it was in the autumn that cattle were fat and ready for sale. Substantial amounts of money must have changed hands at this time. The village was periodically the venue of the circuit court (*justice aire*) for mid-Argyll and Knapdale, and frequently appears as the place where bonds and other legal documents were signed in the seventeenth century. All this indicates the existence of an inn, implying work for ostlers, chamber maids, cooks, etc. Glassary is also reported to have had a schoolmaster prior to 1694, who doubtless lived at Kilmichael (McKerral 1948, p. 157).

None of this would be suspected from the hearth tax roll which merely shows 14 houses in Kilmichael, albeit one with two hearths. It may be concluded that most of the inhabitants were not cultivating the land and that the population was probably augmented by people coming in daily from surrounding farms.

The standard of life in Glassary at this time was primitive, as will be seen more clearly from the description of the houses given below. One commentator wrote:

Those who have large possessions live well; those who have poor ones live poorly. The small farmers, for nine or ten months in the year, make generally two, and sometimes three meals a-day of potatoes, with herrings or milk. Such as can afford it salt a cow in winter, and kill a sheep or two in harvest. Oatmeal pottage, or oatmeal jelly (*sowens*), make commonly the third meal a-day, with milk; and oaten or bear bread, when the potatoes fail, supply their place (Smith 1798, p. 57).

This was written a hundred years after the period under review, so the reference to potatoes needs to be omitted for they had only just arrived in the British Isles. However, the frugal diet would have been augmented from time to time by wild fruits, like bilberries, and probably also fish.

The population of Glassary

The Glassary men between the ages of 16 and 60 years judged suitable for army service ('fencible men') numbered 302 in 1692 (Appendix VIII). From this number, which can be called m , we can make an attempt to estimate the size of the total Glassary population (P) if we know, at least approximately, the proportion of the population (k_1) in the age group 16 to 60 years, and the ratio of males to females ($k_2 = m/f$). Then

$$P = 302 / k_1 k_2$$

For the year 1695 there is a comprehensive population structure available for the town of Lichfield, in England, which gives $k_1 = 0.56$ and ratio of males to females (k_2) equal to 83/100 (Glass & Everley 2008, p. 181). Males are, as usual, outnumbered by females. Thus,

$$m + f = P \text{ and } m/f = 83/100$$

These equations can be combined, eliminating f , to give

$$m = P \cdot (1 + 100/83)^{-1} = 0.453P$$

The total population is then $302 / (0.56 \times 0.45)$, or 1198 men, women and children. It will be noticed that one can get a rough estimate of the population by simply multiplying the number of fencible men by 4.

This estimate of the total population, P , is subject to considerable uncertainty for three reasons. Firstly, the ages of the men recruited were estimated by a recruiting officer mainly intent on getting suitable men for the army rather than statistical nicety. Secondly, the Lichfield data have been criticised in statistical

grounds (Glass & Eversley 2008, pp.181–183). Lastly, the Lichfield data were drawn from an environment far from rural Glassary. Consequently, the figure for the Glassary population may be in error by ± 50 .

The number of houses (not hearths), in 1691 was 228, giving an average family size of 5.5. If allowance is made for the number omitted by the collector due to inability or reluctance, to pay, which is not stated, the family size would be larger. It has been estimated that in other parts of Scotland only about 65% of houses were listed (Flinn 1977, Table 3.8.6), so the actual number of houses in Glassary might have been as much as $228/0.65 = 350$. The resulting average family size would then be only 3.6 individuals.

These numbers for family members are not out of line with results from the east of Scotland, which for rural parishes was about 5 (Flinn 1977, p. 196). It does not indicate significant overpopulation. Indeed, the list of fencible men in 1692 (Appendix VIII) notes three farms as deserted, i.e., the 3 merkland of Nether Fincharn, the 2 merkland of Craignuir and the 2.5 merkland of Ardnaheir.

The late seventeenth century data give no hint of what was to come. Only a hundred years later, in 1794, the population of Glassary had more than doubled to 2568. The minister of Glassary then wrote that there were seven resident heritors, 5 blacksmiths, 32 weavers, 6 shoemakers, 2 masons, 6 millers, 6 tailors, 6 carpenters, 2 wheelwrights, and 2 surgeons. There were 30 boats engaged in the herring fisheries, employing 120 men. The minister added that 'the rest are employed in farming and herding' (Campbell 1794, vol. 13, pp. 656–657). It is surprising that there is no mention of a merchant or an inn-keeper.

The rapid increase in the population of Glassary was partly the result of the introduction of smallpox vaccination about 1775 (Campbell 1794, p. 658), but mainly the result of immigration from the lowlands. Appendix I shows that in the late seventeenth century, about 15% of the population had lowland surnames (like Black, Whytt). But in 1795 the birth register for Glassary parish shows that about 40% of the children born that year had lowland surnames.

Among the surnames of Gaelic origin, the commonest were Campbell (21%), MacTavish (9%) and MacLauchlan (7%). The Campbells were distributed across the parish, but the MacTavishes (often spelt as McCavish) were concentrated in the southern part, especially at Kilmory and Auchoish.

The lowland families shown in Appendix I very probably arrived in 1646 from Renfrewshire, as a result of the epidemic of typhus mentioned earlier. The surnames Fletcher, Mathie, Speir, Graham and Stewart, in particular, have been shown to have originated in the parish of Paisley Abbey (Stewart 2020). However, families called Stevenson, Black, etc could well have come from other parishes. Furthermore, there are no earlier name lists to exclude the possibility of there being lowland families in Glassary before 1646.

Figure 3. Map of the parish of Kilmichael Glassary showing the principal residences of the heritors in 1688. The base map and the spelling of names derive from the Ordnance Survey of 1876.

Figure 4. Map of the parish of Kilmichael Glassary about 1750, showing the extent of uncultivated land (medium grey tint), arable land (white), and water (pale grey). Natural woodland is ornamented with the symbol L. The map is abstracted from Roy's military survey of Scotland, on a scale of 100 yards to the inch, formed during the years 1747–1755, and now in the British Library map collection (CC.5.a.441). The limits of the parish (not shown on the original map) are indicated by a dotted line.

Agriculture

The miserable state of agriculture in Glassary was neatly summarized by the minister of Glassary in 1794 when he wrote;

The air is generally moist, and the climate rainy, which renders farming here very precarious, and often unprofitable...(Campbell 1794, p. 655).

Most of the parish was quite unsuitable for arable cultivation; it was too rocky and cold. There were only 14 square kilometres of arable and 3 square kilometres of natural woodland (Fig. 4). Inland the hills rise to 450 m (1480 ft), the temperature rapidly falls, and annual rainfall increases to over 2000 mm. In late summer, when the heather flowers, the hills would have provided a fine sight, but in winter the rock and heather disappeared under snow. Only on the lowest ground is the climate mild. As a consequence of this harsh climate there have never been permanent settlements above 200 m (James 2009, Figs. 1.3 & 5.23).

Stock

The animals possessed by the farmers of Glassary can be seen from what was forfeited from 105 rebels in 1685 (Appendix V). It averaged 5 cows each, while every second man had a sheep or a horse. Oxen, used for ploughing in eastern Scotland at this time, were absent. So, too, were mules and donkeys. The cows provided milk for making butter and cheese. It may be assumed that these animals were easily seen and their owners identified. There is no mention of any beef cattle in the hills, which would have been quite invisible except to their owners. These animals, however, appear (as 'marts') in the feu duties of the heritors, along with the butter, cheese and oatmeal coming from the tenants (Appendix III). Marts, it should be explained, refer to Martinmas cattle, usually slaughtered on the 11 November.

So few bullocks appear among the heritors feu duties that it seems they originated as calves born to the few cows owned by the tenants (see Appendix V). One of these calves, at a year old, presumably went to pay the rent and another was sold for cash. Sheep sometimes appear among the feu duties (Appendix III), but usually are absent, indicating that they were for domestic use only. There is no sign of extensive cattle rearing, even though a century later the minister of Glassary recorded that the parish had 3200 'black cattle' (bullocks) and 12,000 black-faced sheep (Campbell 1794, p. 659). The reason was that in seventeenth century Glassary the forage crops needed to sustain the animals during the winter (clover, beans, peas and turnips) were not used. Consequently, over-wintered animals often died of starvation.

The sheep mentioned above were not the large animals with black faces to be seen today in the hills, which were brought to Glassary from the Lowlands about 1780 (Campbell 1794, p. 655). They were, rather, small animals more like those of the Shetland Islands, weighing about 10 kg. In a late eighteenth century account of life in Argyllshire they were described as

small, intelligent creatures covered with fine wool, each answering to its name, and milked as well as the cows. We were obliged to fold them at night, because of the numerous foxes and wild cats that prowled about freely (Grant 1919, p. 147).

In Glassary this breed was reported in 1794 to be 'much on the decrease, and only kept by some of the smaller tenants' (Campbell 1794, p. 660).

Throughout the west of Scotland it was customary to take advantage of the warm summer weather to pasture cows and sheep in the shielings—areas of grass lost among the rock and heather, or flanking streams. Women were sent to look after the stock and make butter and cheese, while living in temporary shelters. These shelters were rebuilt annually, the walls made of peat, all resting on a stone foundation, and the rooves thatched from heather. Today only the foundations remain. Called *airigh* in Gaelic, these shielings frequently appear as place names in the hills, but not above 200 m (James 2009, Fig. 5.23). For example, the estate map of Shirvan shows that the farm of Ballimore extended for 3.5 km northwards from the coast to hills 200 metres high, one of which is called 'Airi Ballimhor' (Buchanan 1831). Other shieling names on Ordnance Survey maps of Glassary are Airidh Ard, Loch Airidh na Craige, Gleann Airidh, and Creag Airidh.

Cereals

Most of the arable land was on the lower slopes of the hills where there was natural drainage. Much of the flat land near the River Add remained swamp until it was drained in the early nineteenth century.

The main crops were oats and barley. The oats, milled to give oatmeal, appear in the feu duties and teinds of the heritors (Appendix III), but the barley does not. Its production, however, is attested by the presence of millers, described in Appendix IX as maltmen. They were milling barley as the first stage in the production of whisky. It may be deduced that the barley grown was no more than that needed for the local production of whisky and ale.

Rents

In the absence of rental contracts for Glassary the evaluation of gross farm income can only be attempted via the teinds. The teind dues were a tenth of the products of the land, paid in kind by a tenant, and intended to support the church. The heritor's duty was to collect the teinds and transmit them to the titular. The Glassary teinds for 1670 are recorded in a writ of 1673 served on the tenants and heritors of Glassary by 'Charles Maitland of Haltoun, Treasurer Depute, proprietor and superior of the lands aftermentioned, and titular of the teinds'. It resulted from failure of the heritors to pay the feu duties and teinds for the years 1668, 1669 and 1670, due to doubts about the legal rights of Haltoun, and in particular his claim to be titular of the teinds. The writ, apart from identifying the heritors and tenants, also gives details of the feu duties and teinds outstanding (Appendices III & IV).

It can be deduced from Appendix IV that the teind in Glassary ranged from £5 to £16 Scots per merkland, with an average of £9. Assuming that the valuation from which the teinds were calculated was up to date, the gross return for a merkland would then be about £90 and the teind £9. The rent of a farm would normally be a third of the gross income (Black 1893, pp. 64 & 75), which for Glassary is £27. The average valued rent of a merkland in the 1688 land tax rolls for Argyll was £29 (Appendix VI), and for Glassary it is the same (NRS E106/3/1/13), so the calculated rental for Glassary is by no means exceptional. This rental represents a return of about 5.5% on the capital value of a merkland, assuming the value of the 3 merkland of Ullian given earlier is representative.

The houses

Houses from the seventeenth century may survive in Glassary but cannot be certainly identified. The ruins seen so frequently today are mostly nineteenth century dry stone buildings with chimneys, clearly built by masons. Any earlier houses lacked chimneys.

An example of such a house, extant in 1789, and partly restored in 1979, is preserved at Auchindrain folk museum, which lies just a kilometre beyond the north-eastern extremity of Glassary. The house, called building G, can be taken as representative of a seventeenth century peasant house. Its present appearance and ground plan are shown in Fig. 5. It was basically a single room, with a partition separating the cow from its owner. There was no chimney. The fire served only for cooking, which goes some way to explain why more than 95% of the 228 houses in Glassary had only one hearth (Appendix VII). Nine private houses had two hearths, perhaps for extended families. One house had three hearths and, since it belonged to one of the heritors, MacLauchlan of Fernoch, may have had a fire purely for the pleasure of its warmth. For everyone else the labour involved in cutting and transporting peats would be enough to extinguish the thought of such extravagance.

The absence of even one window may seem strange, but since the house served to protect its occupants from rain and wind, like a tent, a window was useless. In any case, glass in the seventeenth century was a luxury used in the great houses of the nobility and in some townhouses, but certainly not among the peasantry (Turnbull 2001, pp. 54–55).

Figure 5 A. Auchindrain folk museum, ground plan of building G. The dark grey tint shows the original building, the part tinted pale grey is a nineteenth century addition. The hearth area is dotted. The north-east end of the building was reserved for a cow.

Figure 5 B. Auchindrain folk museum, building G seen from outside (Dixon 2018, Fig. 116).

Figure 5 C. Auchindrain folk museum, building G seen from just inside the southernmost door, looking north-east.

A description of an Argyll peasant house about 1798 shows building G at Auchindrain to have been typical.

These cottages are in general miserable habitations. They are built of round stones, without any cement, thatched with sods, and sometimes heath: they are generally, though not always, divided by a wicker partition into two apartments, in the larger of which the family reside; it serves likewise as a sleeping room for them all. In the middle of this room is the fire made of peat, placed on the floor; and over it, by means of a hook, hangs the pot for dressing the victuals. There is frequently a hole in the roof to allow exit to the smoke, but this is not directly over the fire, on account of the rain, and very little of the smoke finds its way out of it, the greatest part, after having filled every corner of the room, coming out of the door, so that it is almost impossible for anyone unaccustomed to it, to breath in the hut. The other apartment, to which you enter by the same door, is reserved for cattle and poultry, when these last do not choose to mess and lodge with the family (Garnett 1800, vol. 1, p. 121)

The interior of the thatch was blackened with tar deposited by the smoke. Such dwellings, once common in Scotland, were called 'black houses'. There was no risk of the thatch catching fire, for a peat fires produce neither flame nor spark. The introduction of windows appears to have changed living conditions but little. The description of the interior of a black house with a window in Colonsay in 1887 shows it to have been quite as repellant as the one described above, even though the author described its inhabitants as living 'a healthy and happy life' (Murray 1887, pp. 49–50).

The building illustrated in Fig. 5 contains masonry weighing about 60 metric tons. This must have been brought downhill from a quarry, on horse-drawn slipes. Slipes, or sledges, were commonly used in Kintyre in the seventeenth century for moving peats and other heavy weights across rough ground (Smith 1798, p. 60; McKerral 1948, p. 141). They were still being used in Argyll less than a hundred years ago, and in other countries until recently (Stewart 2015, Fig. 17).

Mills

Of the 6 mills listed in 1691 none today survive. Judging from their locations they were of the type with a vertical axis, suitable for very small streams. Such mills were once common all over Europe; a Scottish example is described by Cruden (1948). Their design is shown diagrammatically in Fig. 6. The mills were often sited where there was a natural waterfall; a fall of no more than 2 m would be sufficient. The water was directed into a vertical chute, from which it issued in a jet at the bottom, striking the paddles. The turning paddles were mounted on a vertical shaft attached rigidly to the upper millstone, or runnerstone, which turned at a speed determined by the water flow. The lower millstone, or bedstone, remained stationary. Provision was made for slightly raising or lowering the runner stone to cope with either oats or barley, and to determine the quality of the flour.

Figure 6. Diagrammatic plan and section of a water mill with a vertical axis, sited over a natural waterfall. The chute is depicted as vertical, but in the absence of a waterfall or a dam it would be inclined.

The vertical mills of Glassary survived well into the nineteenth century. In 1750 there were nine (Appendix X), and in 1802 there were seven; at Ballimore Aird, Ballimore Kilmichael, Ederlin, Gortanrannoch, Silvercraigs, Drum and Auchnashelloch (NRS E106/3/3/11–12). Langland’s survey of Argyllshire, published the same year, also shows mills at Rhudle and Ullian. But by 1871 there remained only the Rhudle mill, with a horizontal axis and overshot wheel.

Kilns

The cereals to be milled had to be dried, since the crop could only be harvested by hand, slowly, and in a rainy climate. Kilns for this purpose are well-known in Scotland (cf. Gibson 1989). An example from Argyll is shown in Fig. 7. Kilns survived well into the nineteenth century in northern Scotland, and also in Argyll even though they do not figure in the 1750 valuation roll (Appendix X), and Smith (1798) makes no mention of them being a traditional feature of the agricultural scene.

Another use for kilns was the production of whisky by roasting malt. The kiln master at Kilinochonach listed in the 1692 hearth tax roll, Malcolm McCallum, was described as a maltman in 1709 (Appendix IX). This suggests that this kiln and the other three with kiln masters (Kilmory, Dunamuck, Ballimore) were being used in the same way. Ballimore had two kilns, one with a master and one without, the latter perhaps used by the tenants for drying grain. Barley malt was also used for producing beer by a simple process requiring neither a kiln, nor distillation. There were ale houses recorded in Drum in 1670 (McKechnie 1938, p. 386) and there were probably many others.

Figure 7. Diagrammatic section of an eighteenth century cereal drying kiln, based on an example about 3 km north of Crarae (NN020025), studied by Grant et al. (1983). The kiln basin was excavated in an artificial hillock and lined with dry-stone masonry. The cereals were spread over a wicker platform covering the mouth of the kiln, and heated from beneath. The inclined flue was 4.5 m long. The cereals were protected from rain by a lightly constructed dome or cone, which has not survived.

The number of kilns was probably more than the 20 listed in the hearth tax roll, for 5 mills are noted as having two hearths each, which might suggest that a kiln too small for assessment was a necessary adjunct to a mill. This accords with a description of mills in Shetland written in 1895;

alongside most of these mills were small kilns, only two or three feet square, though sometimes circular. The grain was dried on a floor made of basket work, covered with straw to prevent the grain falling through. But this precaution was not always successful, and the burning of the kilns was a common event (Ross 1974, p. 45).

Roads and bridges

There were neither roads nor bridges in Glassary. The tracks shown on Roy's map of 1750 were suitable for hooves and feet, but not carriages or carts. Even in 1785 there were only three carts in Glassary, all at the iron works at Furnace on Loch Fyne-side, established in 1755 to exploit the native woodland. Even Campbeltown only had 6 carts (NRS E326/7/1/5). By this time most Lowland parishes had many more, for example Paisley parish had 64 carts in 1787 (NRS E326/7/4/191).

Cattle driven to Kilmichael market from farther south came along the track from Dunardry, in Knapdale, and went north. To reach Kilmichael they had to ford the River Add; the bridge here was not built until 1737.

The Kilmichael market over and their cattle rested, the Kintyre, Knapdale and Islay drovers faced the next stage up Loch Fyne of their long march to Falkirk. Roy's map, already referred to, marks the route they followed up the valley of the Add to its head waters to join the track which crosses the Leckan Muir from Kilneuair making for Inveraray. 'By this route', says a Memorial of 1807 urging improvement of the road, 'the inhabitants of Knapdale, Jura, Islay, Colonsay, North Lorne and adjacent islands take their cattle to the Low country with hardly a single exception (Haldane 1952, pp. 97-98).

Drovers relate that it took a good week to drive the cattle from Glassary to Falkirk (Haldane 1951, p. 98 note 1).

Crime & Punishment

The simple life is not without its temptations and a surprising number of cases concerning Glassary men were brought before the Argyll Justiciary Court. The surviving case notes for 1685 and 1709 make interesting reading. The trial on 21 December 1709 involved 72 men from Glassary accused of crimes in conflict with the 'penal statutes' (Appendix IX). Ten men were not described as guilty, presumably acquitted. Only three men were accused of 'battery' i.e. physical assault. All three had been remitted from Campbell of Auchinbrecks's baron court ('Cast Court') held at Kilmichael Glassary, which evidently felt the cases fell outside its competence. The rest of the men were accused of illegal fishing, cutting timber without permission, moor-burning, borrowing someone's horse without 'allowance', using false weights, and the like. Considering that more than half the men of Glassary were armed it is surprising that there was not more armed violence (cf. Appendix VIII). The flavour of the court proceedings is conveyed by the appeal for clemency by John McColl in Asknish (Kilmelford):

In ane Justice Court holden at Killmichell [Glassary] in December last the [said] petitioner was Fyned in Ten pounds Scots mony for cutting of ane fishing road [rod] ... he having nothing wherewith to pay the [said] Fyne but Five goats which is the only sustenance he has for Family and five small children...

The petitioner's representative added:

May it therefore please yr Lordship to consider the petitioners miserable and necessitous condition and to absolve him from the [said] Fyne imposed upon him for cutting of the [said] fishing road which the petitioner made use of for fishing to help his poor Family (NRS SC54/17/2/34/10, p. 7).

The fine was commuted.

Reflections

Glassary in the seventeenth century presents a grim picture of primitive agriculture and dreadful housing, not unlike that in the rest of Europe at that time. An unstable political environment did not help.

There are no agricultural statistics for Glassary, but in eastern Scotland over the period 1673–1692 oats yielded 3.0 times the seed sown (Young 2007, pp. 55 & 58). With a sowing rate of 240 kg/ha this means a yield of 720 kg/ha. In Europe today the ratio and the yield are ten times greater, due to better preparation of the seed bed, carefully selected seed, and the use of fertilisers. It is, however, easy to find poor cereal yields like those in seventeenth century Glassary in the developing world today, especially Africa.

The seventeenth century black houses can hardly have fostered the 'healthy and happy life' mentioned earlier. The unhealthy effect of such a polluted atmosphere is particularly evident in the third world today. Globally at least 2.4 billion people are exposed to the toxic smoke of biomass fuel, typically burned

inefficiently in poorly ventilated indoor stoves or fireplaces (FIRS 2021, p. 5). The smoke and fumes particularly affect the lungs of women and young children, gathered around the hearth, who then get bronchitis and pneumonia, and often die. Data published by the World Health Organization show that in low-income countries one of the two main causes of death is lower respiratory disease, due to smoke. The dense smoke of the black houses in Glassary was probably as lethal as anywhere on Earth, and quite sufficiently so to nullify the beneficial effect of the pristine air outside. Little improvement seems to have occurred during the following century, for the minister of Glassary wrote in 1794

Coughs, and rheumatisms are frequent, particularly among the lower class of people when advanced in years, which is not surprising, when the huts in which they for the most part live, and the climate are considered....There are sometimes very bad fevers among the lower class, commencing generally in the spring months...and often prove very mortal (Campbell 1794, p. 658).

Here we are seeing not only the effect of lung infections, but perhaps also malaria—due to the prevalence of swampy land near the rivers.

The other cause of death in low-income countries, and doubtless also formerly in Glassary, was neonatal conditions. All this is in marked contrast to middle and high income countries, where most deaths today are due to heart disease and stroke.

If Glassary peasant houses were so unhealthy one might wonder why their owners did not fit windows, but, as will have been clear from the description of a black house in 1887, a window does not solve the problem. Chimneys would have been a solution, but required skill to construct, and were regarded with suspicion because it was thought they would not leave room round the fire for the little people. This may sound strange, but the supernatural was ever present in the Highlands well into the nineteenth century.

Needless to say, the wealthier inhabitants of Glassary did not live in black houses. Carnasserie castle, where Campbell of Achinbreck lived prior to 1685, had fireplaces (Historic Environment Scotland 2020, Fig. 3). The mansion at Gairloch, whence the family moved in 1692, no longer exists, but was doubtless well provided with both fireplaces and windows. Another notable building was the manse. When the erudite Mr Daniel Campbell (1665–1722) was appointed minister of Kilmichael Glassary in 1691 he evidently felt the need for a decent house, especially since he was just about to marry. The new minister received

400 merks from the Synod which enabled him to finish the building of a manse, erected chiefly at his own expense, one of the first manses in the country, and well known for its 'nineteen windows' (Scott 1923, p. 6).

The minister's wife was Jean, daughter of Patrick Campbell of Torblaren (Campbell 1864). As an illustration of those tempestuous times it can be related that about 1685, when Jean was but a girl, she was travelling in a carriage with

Lady Henrietta Lindsay, the wife of Sir Duncan Campbell of Auchinbreck, an ally of the Earl of Argyll, when they were stopped by royalist soldiers. The two women were carrying a letter implicating Sir Duncan in the plot to overthrow the King. Jean Campbell quickly chewed and swallowed the letter (Scott 1923, p. 6).

Insecurity also surrounded the tenants in Glassary. In 1685 they were 'vassals' of the Earl of Argyll and were expected to fight for him in his futile attempt to overthrow the Catholic king. But only six years later they were forcibly enlisted in the national army.

The influence of central government was augmented in 1707 with the Union of Scotland with England, and later, between 1726 and 1767, by the construction of military roads and bridges by the British army. The heritable Jurisdiction (Scotland) Act of 1746 was another nail in the coffin of Scottish feudal power, for it eliminated the baron courts. Slowly Scotland was changing from a decentralized feudal state into part of the unitary state we have today.

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Appendix I
**Lowland surnames
in seventeenth century Glassary**

1670	<i>n</i>	1691	<i>n</i>	1692	<i>n</i>
Black	2	Barr	1	Black	2
Brown	2	Black	2	Boyd	1
Clerk	1	Blair	1	Brown	1
Fletcher	1	Boyd	1	Burn	1
Graham	2	Carr [Kerr]	1	Carr [Kerr]	1
King	1	Clark	1	Clark	2
Leitch	8	Crawford	1	Crawford	2
Mathie	2	Dick	1	Cunningham	1
Pollock	3	Elder	1	Dick	1
Speir	1	Galbraith	1	Fleming	1
Stevenson	8	King	1	Galbraith	1
Stewart	3	Leitch	3	Glass	2
Walker	1	Mathie	1	Johnstone	1
		Moodie	1	King	1
		Munro	1	Mathie	1
		Paul	1	Moodie	1
		Pollock	1	Murray	1
		Stevenson	6	Orr	2
		Stewart	3	Paul	2
		White	1	Pollock	1
				Stevenson	6
				Stewart	3
				White	2
Total <i>n</i>	35		30		37
%	18		13		12

n is the number of occurrences. Data sources; 1670, Appendix II; 1691, Appendix VII; 1692, Appendix VIII. Percentages are related to the total number of men in Appendix VIII.

Appendix II

Glassary heritors and tenants in 1670

In: 'Decreet at the instance of Charles Maitland of Haltoun, Treasurer Depute, against Archibald M'Lauchlane of that ilk, and others, for rents and teinds, 27 February 1672', transcribed from McPhaill (1916), pp. 207–211.

Archibald M'Lauchlan of that ilk

Gortengor

John M'Muyer
Neill Mecristall
Duncan M'Vicar
Anna M'Breyne

Drynlea

John M'Intyre
Duncan M'Inleister

Galdanach

Patrick M'Nicoll
Nicol M'Nicoll

Auchnaselloch

Lachlan M'Lauchlane
Neill M'Lauchlane
Alexander M'Lauchlane
Neill Steinsone
Allan M'Lauchlane

Dunnamucke

Neill M'Phune
Archibald M'Phunie
Alexander M'Laertike
Donald M'Alpen
Archibald Leitch
John Leitch
Donald M'blaren

Dariloch

Augustine Lauchlane

Colin Campble of Inerhea

Crare

Duncan Walker
John M'ohenlane
Patrick M'Vicar
John M'Ilmolnaage
Duncan Campble

Garvachie

Alexander M'Tavishe
Dougald M'Tavishe
Donald M'Tavishe
Archibald Campble
John M'Ilvean

Sir Duncan Campble of Auchinbreck

Fincharne Over

Angus Campble
Hew M'Callum
Alexander Campble
Duncan M'Indeor
John M'Indeor
John M'rihirich
John Leitch

Fincharne Nedder & Kilneuar

Kennich M'Kellar
Hew M'Alpen
John Roy M'Keller
Patrick M'Keller
Angus M'Ilmund
Duncan M'Lauchlane

Two Edderlings

Archibald M'Arthur
Robert Broun
Patrick M'Arthur
Donald Campble
Gilbert M'Callum
Neill M'Callum

Two Bravaliches

Walter Graham
Gilbert M'Keoll
Gilbert M'Callum
Donald Baine Vicar
John Oconochar

Donad M'Herreis

Monienirnach

Evar M'Evar
Duncan M'Knockaird
Alexander Grhame
Duncan Fledger

Tunis

Dougald M'Illelevin
John M'Inleister

Two Carrenes

Donald M'Indeor
John Campble
Maraget M'Illworrie

Kirktoun Kirmichell

James Steinsone
John Palloche
Hew M'Illeleave
Duncan M'Ilvernoche
John Steinsone elder
John Steinsone younger

Ballemor Kirmichell

John Steinsone
Robert Speir
William Pulloche
Alexander Steinsone

Patrick Campble of Kilmoir [Kilmory]

Uleyeiffe

Neill Campble
Duncan M'Phadden
Lachlan M'Phadden
John Pulloch

Caiganewar

Archibald M'Intyre

Master Dougald Campble of Barquhill

Barquhill
Gilbert M'Leriche
Hew M'Leriche
Donald M'Leriche
Duncan M'Neill

**Henry Leitch of
Darieranereuch**

Colin M'Lauchlane,
wadsetter of Ardariat

**Archibald
M'Lauchlane of
Craiginteriffe**

Over Sherewaine
Duncan M'Blaren
John M'Dougald V'Alpen
Archibald Broun
Angus M'Innyeir

Nether Shiriewaine
Colin M'Lauchlane
John M'Lauchlane
Martin M'Alfein
John M'Alpen
Donald M'Blaren
John Leitch
Archibald Leitch
Fernoeh
Master John Campble
Auchaharse
Duncan M'Alpen
Duncan Leitch
Hew M'Blaren
John M'Chrytor

**Archibald
M'Lauchlane of
Keuhaniche**

Ducharnan
John Rooych M'Lauchlane
Hew M'Bryne
Over Kames
Gilbert M'Mertein
Lachlan M'Lauchlane
Hew M'Nicoll
Corlaren
Donald Campble
John M'Vicar

Craillmorrull
Donald M'Alpen
Archibald M'Chrytor
Archibald M'Evar

Jean Campble, daughter
& heir of Master Dougald
Campble of Lagge, &
Barbara Lamount his
widow, liferentrix

Glenalpen
Colin Campble
Nether Rudill
Alexander M'Tavishe
Hew M'Oldonich
Cnocknalelit
John M'Vicar
Duncan M'Breyane
Auchinbreck
Alexander McTavishe
John M'Tavishe
John M'Vikam

**Allan M'Lauchlane of
Dunadd & Barokill**

Dunad
Duncan Dow M'Lauchlane
William Steinsone
George Steinsone
John Roy M'Lauchlane
Barnakill
Archibald M'Intyllor
John M'Intyllor
Dunan M'Phaill
John M'Illbreyd

**John Campble of
Auchadacherlike
Neill Campble of Over
Rudill & Moir M'Callum**
his mother

Barill
Archibald Campble
Kilbryde
Fergus M'Herries
John Clerk

Robert Campble,
younger of Silvercraigs,
merchant burges of Glasgow

Nedder Caimes
Robert Campble
Duncan M'Inuyer
Duncan M'Mertein

Carricke
Hew M'Tavishe
Archibald Black
Patrick M'Quhiriche
Archibald M'Killich
Alexander M'Tavishe

Auchnaba
Angus M'Mertein
John Campble
John Steuard
Donald M'Invernocke
Ardnocheirerie
John Mathie, elder
John Mathie, younger
William King

Keirmichellbeg
Evar M'Illloglashe
John M'Quhirich
Donald M'Morten
Alexander Fergusone
Duncan M'Nab
Archibald Campble
John Campble
Ballemore
Partick Campble, younger
Archibald M'Jock
Neill M'Nicoll

Duppenie
Gilbert M'Ilven
Donald M'Phaden
James Lamount
Colin Campble

Blarbuy
John M'Illvernocke
Archibald M'Illvernocke
Neill M'Nicoll
Archibald M'Greigor

Lingartoun
Robert Steuart
Duncan Steuart
Evar M'Obrekin
Malcom M'Niel
Domicolgyne
Donald Campble
Hew M'Aren
Archibald M'Kernocke
Hew M'Sorrill

Donald Lamount of Drum

Menendryan

John Black
Archibald M'Chruytor
Malcolm McEwar
Duncan M'Ewar
Alexander Lamount
Alexander M'Lauchlane
Alexander M'Euar

Alexander M'Taveis of Garvalt

Garvalt

Duncan M'Taveis

Breinhaleichs

Archibald M'Vicar

Auchageyll

Patrick M'Ilvenie

Gilbert M'Arthure

John M'Nokaird

Archibald M'Blaren

Feorling

Dougald Campble

John M'Inleister

Duncan M'Haugh

Cnockalloway

Angus Campble

Dougald Leitch

John M'Ilreave

Angus Keir Campble

Archibald Lamount of Stronalbanach

Angus Campble of Glaswar

John Campble of Leckworie

Duncan M'Ilmun of Fernoch

Alexander M'Ilmun of Kenlochlean

Donald M'Lauchlane of Carnaem

Malcolm Campble of Stroneskear

Archibald Campble of Keernam

Archibald & John McIlmun, portioners of Sockock

John Campble of Barmeloch

Neill M'Keller of Laternamust

Appendix III
**Some Glassary feu and teind duties
for 1668, 1669 and 1670**

From McPhaill (1916, pp. 211–217)

Feuer	m	Feu duty	Teind duty
Angus Campble Gleswell, Succoth & Letternamult	8 1/2	£48-6-8 2 3/4 marts = £44-0-0	£30-13-4 14 bolls meal
Archibald Campble Kernan & Achalike	5	£14-13-4 one mart=£16-0-0 5 stones of cheese=£8-6-8	£6-0-0 5 bolls meal
Donald M'Lauchlan Achagarren & Carnaem	3 1/2	£11-13-4 3/4 mart= £12-0-0 1 3/4 stones of butter= £5-16-0 1 stone of cheese= £1-13-4 3 kain wedders= £6-0-0	10 merks 3 bolls 2 firlots meal
Malcolm Campble Stronoskeer	3	£13-10-0 1 mart= £16-0-0	£6-13-4 8 bolls meal
John Campble Leckquhorie	3	£26-13-4 1 mart= £20-0-0	10 merks 4 bolls meal
Archibald Lamount Stronalbanoch	2	£10-0-0 1/2 mart= £8-0-0 1 1/4 stones of butter= £4-13-4	10 merks 2 bolls 2 firlots meal
Duncan M'IImun Fernoeh	2	£5-6-8 1/4 mart= £5-0-0 1 kain wedder= £1-6-8	£3-0-0 1 boll 2 firlots meal

Farm valuation is given in merklands (**m**). Money is in pounds Scots (£), shillings and pence. A merk is £0-13-4 Scots. A mart is an abbreviation of Martinmas bullock, and a wedder is a castrated male sheep. One stone weighs 6.35 kg. A boll of oatmeal weighed 63.5 kg and was equivalent to 4 firlots. The value of a boll of meal in eastern Scotland at this time was about £5 Scots (Flinn 1977, p.). The value of one merk was £0-13-4 Scots in 1670. The six farms listed are the only ones mentioned in the writ of 1673 for which both the feu and teind duties are listed, and the number a merklands is known from Appendix X.

Appendix IV
**Some Glassary teind duties
for the years 1668, 1669 and 1670**

From McPhaill (1916), pp. 213–218

Robert Campbell, merchant burgess of
Glasgow [35m]
Killmichellbeg, Balemore, Fingartone,
Drumcolgine, Blairbusse, Dupen,
Carrickes, Keames, Ardnaherren, Achnaba
£60-14-0 + 40 bolls meal

Angus Campble of Glesswer
Glesswell, Succoth and Letternamult
[8½m]
£30-13-4 + 14 bolls meal

Malcolm Campbell of Stronoskeer
Stronoskeer [3m]
£6-13-4 + 8 bolls meal

Jean Campble heir to
Mr Dougald Campble of Lagge
& **Barbara Lamount**, her mother
Nether Ruddill, Knocknacult and
Achnabreck
£8-0-0 + 6 bolls meal

Jean Campble heir to
Mr Dougald Campble of Lagge
& **Barbara Lamount**, her mother
Auchinkeill
£4-13-4 + 2 bolls 2 firlots meal

Neill Campble of Over Ruddill
Over Ruddill, Barryly & Killbryde [6m]
£11-13-4 + 10 bolls meal

Archibald Lamont of Stronalbanoch
Stronalbanoch [2m]
10 merks + 2 bolls 2 firlots meal

Alexander M'Ilmun
Kenlochlean [1½m]
£4-0-0 + 1 boll 2 firlots meal

Duncan M'Ilmund
Fernoch [2m]
£3-0-0 + 1 boll 2 firlots meal

Colin Campble
Inverlea, Crare, and Galvachine
£12-0-0 + 8 bolls meal

Archibald Campble
Kernan and Achalike [5m]
£6-0-0 + 5 bolls meal

Donald M'Lauchlane
Carnaem and Achagarren [3½m]
10 merks + 3 bolls 2 firlots meal

Patrick Campble of Killmorie
Killmorie and Ulicht [6m]
£14-0-0 + 7 bolls meal

Archibald M'Lauchlane of Craighturrofe
Over & Nether Shirewaynes [3¼m]
£11-0-0 + 19 bolls meal

Archibald M'Lauchlane of Craighturrofe
Fernoch and Achahoist [5m]
£9-0-0 + 9 bolls meal

Alexander Lamount
Mondryane [4m]
£9-0-0 + 6 bolls meal

Alexander Lamount
Drum [3m]
£6-0-0 + 3 bolls meal

Archibald M'Lauchlane of that Ilk
Dunnamucke and Auchinselloch [10m]
£21-6-8 + 13 bolls meal

Archibald M'Lauchline of that Ilk
Drynlea, Gortanagour and Galdanach [5¾m]
£10-0-0 + 4 bolls victual

Archibald M'Lauchline of Killbewchanath
Killbewhanath, Dewcharnane and Over
Kaimes
£12-0-0 + 8 bolls meal

Allan M'Lauchline of Dunade
Dunade and Barnakyll [5m]
£10-0-0 + 8 bolls meal

Duncan Campble
Achatacherliche [1 1/2m]
£2-0-0 + 3 bolls meal

John Campble of Strondore
Arblaran and Carrine
10 merks + 5 bolls meal

Master Dougald Campble, minister at
Knabdaill
Barchylle [2m]
£4-0-0 + 2 bolls meal

Henry M'Inleitch
Darenanirnach
£3-0-0 + 1 boll meal

Neill Campble of Craigmiriall
Craigniriall [2m]
£3-6-8 + 2 bolls meal

Colin M'Lauchlane
Ardrie [2m]
£6-13-4 + 2 firlots meal

Archibald Campble of Kernene
Knockalloway, Achagyll and Feoline [8m]
£23-0-0 + 8 bolls 2 firlots meal

Archibald M'Lauchlane of that Ilk
Darcloch
£4-0-0 + 5 bolls meal

John Campble
Leckquhorie [3m]
10 merks + 4 bolls meal

Farm valuation is in merklands (m). Money is in pounds Scots (£), shillings and pence. A merk is £0-13-4 Scots. A boll of oatmeal weighed 63.5 kg and was equivalent to 4 firlots. One stone weighs 6.35 kg A wedder is a castrated male sheep. Original spellings have been retained.

Appendix V

List of the Glassary Rebels

whose stock was declared to be forfeited at a court
held by the Marquis of Atholl at Inveraray 12 October 1685.

Transcribed in McTavish (1935), pp. 18–20.

Cames in Aird	Inverhea
Neill McKarn...9.3.0	Archibald McIntyre...2.0.0
– McLaiste...8.0.0	Gilbert McBlarren...4.0.0
Carrick	John Ben Mc Illephatrick...2.0.0
Angus McEwin...2.2.0	Stronalbanich
John Campbell...5.1.2	John McNokaird...10.1.5
John McKerras...1.8.0	Gilbert McMartine...2.0.0
Duncan McChrutar...2.1.0	John McIllevin...4.0.0
Patrick McChrutar...4.1.0	ffeorline
Achnibaa	Angus Campbell...11.2.8
Donald Fergusone...5.2.2	John McIllevin...15.0.0
Ballimore	Minart
Donald Johnstone...8.1.0	Hugh McNicoll...4.0.6
Killmichellbeg	Donald Campbell...3.0.0
Robert Fergusone...2.1.0	Donald McInleach...2.0.0
Duncan Campbell...8.3.12	John McChrutar...2.0.0
Blairbuie	John McIllevin...2.0.0
William King...18.2.0	Duncan McVicar...4.0.0
Lengartane	Gartinronich
Duncan Campbell...8.2.3	Donald McChlerich...1.0.0
Duncan McKarran...1.2.0	Ardchastellmore
John Campbell...3.1.5	John McIvir...3.0.0
Duncholdgine	Ardchastell begg
Duncan McNicolle...10.2.3	Neill McInleach...2.0.0
Donald Campbell...8.0.0	Achoiss
John McCarran...10.2.0	John McCavish...4.1.0
Dupen	Monidren
Donald McIlmun...8.2.0	Ard McCavish...5.1.0
Donald McNiccoll...8.0.3	Duncan McEvar...8.1.5
Gallanich	Sorle Lamont...4.1.0
Archibald McNiccoll...8.3.0	Craigmurell
Gortingour	Malcolm McOlea...2.0.1
Rorie McTavis...12.2.5	Alexr McCavish...2.0.0
Dryinlea	Uyla
Patrick McNicoll...16.2.0	James Stevison...3.1.0
Crarea	Ballimore
Neill McCavish...8.0.5	James Jamison...3.0.0
Patrick McCavish...4.0.0	

Kirktoun of Kilmichell	Letternamult
John Stevinson...4..1..0	Malcolme McKellar...3..0..0
Keirnanmor	ffernoch
Archibald McNicoll...6..0..0	Angus McIlmun...2..0..0
Duncan McOleaven...2..0..0	Kinlochlan
Alexr Campbell...2..0..0	Robert McPhail...3..0..0
Darinloch	Lekuarie
Donald Bain McVicar...4..0..0	Malcolm Campbell...10..0..0
Torblarin	John Stevinsone...10..0..0
Charles Mc Ilmund...2..0..0	Moninvernich
Wm Steinson...6..2..0	Neill McInleish...4..0..0
Carron	Dwnamuk
Alexr McEvar...3..0..0	Allan McLauchlane...7..0..0
Barquhyll	Angus McIntylor...9..0..0
John McLeich...4..1..0	Alexr McLaertich...9..0..0
Charles McIlmun...6..1..0	Achinshelich
ffincharn Ichtarach	Ronald McLauchlan...9..0..0
John McIlelein...4..0..0	Barnokeil
Dougall McIlmun...4..0..0	Dugald McEivir...8..0..0
ffincharnwachter	Charles McEiver...8..0..0
Gilbert McCallum...4..0..0	Dunad
Neill Leich...2..0..0	Allan McLauchlan...12..5..0
Donald Campbell...2..0..0	Donnald McPhun...6..0..0
Soccach	Wm Pollick...5..1..0
John McIlmun...1..0..0	Kaimes in Keillunchinich
John Barr...1..0..0	Lauchlan McLauchlan...3..0..5
Lagg	Lauchlan McLevin...4..1..0
John McChruter...5..0..0	Ducharnane
Lauchlan McCavish...4..0..0	Donald McLauchlan...2..1..0
Glasvar	Ardarie
Gilbert McCapen...6..0..0	Duncan McKellar...15..0..0
Barwullune	Dugald McKellar...15..0..0
Duncan McLaverine...6..0..0	fernoch
Patrick McIllevin...4..0..4	Neill McKavish...2..1..0
Duncan McIllevin...3..1..0	John Stevinsone...1..0..0
John Campbell...13..0..0	Nether Bravallich
John McLulich...6..1..0	John McKellar...6..1..0
Stronesker	John Campbell...4..0..0
Duncan Roy Campbell...3..1..0	Garveichie
Dugall Clerk...3..0..0	John McIllester...12..2..0
John Campbell...2..0..0	John McLauchlan...8..0..0
Dugald Campbell...5..0..0	

Names are followed by the number of cows, horses (including mares) and sheep forfeited. Note tht Neil McCavish in Crarae had 12 goats in addition to 8 cows and 5 sheep.

Appendix VI

Glassary heritors in 1688

National Records of Scotland, MS. E106/3/1/7, Land Tax rolls for Argyll, vol. 1, pp. 12–13

Earl of Lauderdale (proppertie of Auchagyle)	2½m/£60.4.4
Laird of McLauchlan	5m/£224.8.10
Angus Campbell of Glassvar	4½m/£146.4.4
John Campbell of Barmolloch	5m/£114.17.8
Neil McKellar of Lettirnamol	2m/£92.4.4
Duncan McCavish of Garvalt	3m/£56.17.8
Charles Campbell of Stroneskir	3m/£136.0.0
John and Duncan McIlmunes, portioners of Soccoth	3m/£68.0.0
Alexander Campbell of Leckwarie	3m/£76.13.4
Colin McLauchlan of Auchnayarren [Auchayerran]	5½m/£132.17.8
Charles McIlmun of Fernoch	1½m/£37.6.8
Donald McCallum of Overrudil	6m/£179.15.6
Zacharie McCallum of Knockalva	2½m/£68.8.10
Archibald Lamont of Stronalbanich	2½m/£99.6.8
Mr Patrick Campbell of Torblaren	4m/£124.8.10
David Campbell of Innerhea [Inverae]	7½m/£152.0.0
Archibald Campbell of Feorlin	3m/£109.6.8
Robert Campbell of Silvercraigs	24m/£409.6.8
Lady Silvercraigs for Duncholgan & Lingarton	10½m/£195.2.2
Mr William McLauchlan of Fernoch	2m/£118.13.4
John Lamont of Monydrean	7m/£206.13.4
Ivor Campbell of Auchatahelich	1½m/£55.2.2
John McVicar of Brencbellies	5m/£141.6.8
Nicoll McNicol of Gortonagour [Goatfield]	5m/£148.17.8
Donald Campbell of Killmorie	18m/£395.8.10
Alexander McCanish wadsetter of Auchachoise	3m/£93.2.2
Mr Duncan Campbell of Barqhill [Barrachuile]	3m/£34.8.10
Alexander Campbell of Kirnans	5m/£199.11.0
Coline Campbell of Glennan	6m/152.17.6

Archibald McLachlan of Craig (for tuo Sheirvuans)	7m/£221.15.6
Auchinbreck's property now pertaing to the King	52m/£1202.6.8
Archibald McLachlan of Kelleneuchanich	6m/£270.4.4
Nether Rudil, Auchinshelloch, Knocknaheilt, & Tunns now pertaining to his Mattie [Majesty]	13m/£350.13.4
Miln of Sheirvuane	£54.4.4
Dunadd now belonging to Balloquhan	5m/£210.4.4
Fernoch Kenlochlean pertaining to his Mattie [Majesty]	2m/£44.8.10

Land values are given in merklands (**m**) and assessed rentals in pounds Scots (£), shillings and pence. The total valuation for Glassary was 238 merks, or £6986 Scots.

Appendix VII
Hearth Tax Roll for Glassary 1691

Transcribed from National Records of Scotland MS. E69/3/1 pp. 19–24

**Ane List of Monedreans Lands
in the paroach of Glaseri**

Monedrean

John Lamont fier therof
John Lamont tenent ther
Alexr mcCavish
Marie mcOlvea
Georg Whytt
Ard mcVicare
Donald mcIlglase
Janet Lamont
Duncan mcCarran
Ane kilne

Drum

Alexr Lamont
Hew mcCavish
Ard mcVicare
William Stewart
Allexr Campbell
Christin Campbell

Achadaherlich

Iver Campbell (2)
Robert Paull
Ane milne

Achachoise

Allexr mcCavish
Donald mcCavish
Lauchlan mcCavish
Hew mcCavish
Ane kilne

Kilmorie

Duncan Campbell
Duncan mcNiccoll
Alexr Campbell
John mcCarran
Lauchlan mcCavish
Donald mcCavish house & kilne (2)
Donald mcCavish wright

Kilmichell beg

Duncan Campbell
Robert Elder

Patrick mcCavish
Hew mcIlester

Minart

Duncan mcVicare
John mcNokeard
Gilbert mcMartin
Hew mcNiccoll
Duncan mcIlvane
John mcInoweater

Wila

Donald Campbell
James Carr
Katrinee Campbell
Ane kilne

Laglingarten

Collin Campbell (2)
Iver mcVreatin
John Campbell

Duncholgin

Duncan mcLauchlan
John mcCavish
John Stewart
Duncan mcCarran

Kilmichell beg

Robert ffergusson
Angus mcIlvernock
Hew Black
Lauchlan mcCavish

Lecknorie

Allexr Campbell
Ane kilne
Angus mcIlmun
Ard Campbell
John mcNiccoll

Over Rudill

Donald mcCallum (2)
Duncan mcCallum
Donald mcIlephadricke
Ane kilne

Kilbryd

Ard Litch

Duncan mcGalogalich

Baryll

Patrick Campbell

Ane kilne

Torblaran

Charles mcIlmun

Tamas Dick

Ard mcNiccoll

Allexr mcCavish

Ane kilne

Carran

Charles mcIlmun

Barg[ui]ll

Allexr Campbell

Dougall Campbell

Kilanochanichs lands

Ard mcLauchlan (2)

Donald mcffun

Donald mcCallum

Malcolm mccallums house & kilne (2)

Over Cames

John mcLauchlan

Lauchlan mcLauchlan elder

Lauchlan mcLauchlan younger

Hew mcIlester

Dowchernan

Gilbert mcLauchlan (2)

Dunamuck

Lauchlan mcLauchlan

Allan mcLauchlan

Ronald mcLauchlan

Dougall mcLauchlan

Charles Campbell

Neill mcCavish

Dougall mcPhadan

Allan mcLauchlan for house & kilne (2)

Allexr mcLawrtich for house & milne (2)

Glasvars lands

John Campbell therof

Charles Campbell

Malcolm mcIlmun

Dougall mcCavish

John Campbell tenant

John mcCavish

Iver Campbell

Duncan mcIlmun

Gilbert mcCapin

Ane kilne

Johne Barr for his house & milne (2)

**Ane List of Lady Barbrecks
joynter in Glasarie paroach
for payeing of the hearths**

Neather Rowdill

Donald Campbell (2)

Donald mcIlmun

Lauchlan mcInucater

Ard Blair

Ane kilne

Achnibreck

Duncan Campbell

Ard mcLawartich

Allexr mcCavish

Neill Litch

Mr William McLauchlans lands

ffernoch

Mr William mcLauchlan (3)

Ane milne and milne house (2)

Silvercraigs lands

Balimore

John Campbell (2)

Gillish mcIlvernocke

Allexr Stewart

John Black

Ard Campbell

Donald ffergusson

Carrick

John Mathie

Allexr mcAllester

John mcKerras

Ard Black

The ferrie

Margaret Campbell

Malcom Gresich

Arднаherir

Patrick Campbell (2)

Cames

Ard Campbell

John Stinson

Duncan mcChrutir

Paterick mcChrutir

Blarbuj

Duncan mcffail

Dougall mcffail

Duppen

Duncan mcLauchlan
 John Campbell
 Dougall Campbell
 Iver Campbell
 Jo[h]n Mudie for his house & milne (2)

Crarae

Ard Campbell
 Neill mcNeill
 Donald Crawford
 John mcLory[me]r
 Duncan mcOmul

Barmolloch

Malcom Campbell
 Patrick mcOlean
 Duncan mcStuin
 Duncan mcOlvorrie
 John Campbell
 Ane kilne

**Kilberies lands
in Glasserie paroach****Achinselich**

Georg Stinsone
 Lauchlan mcLauchlan
 Allan mcLauchlan
 Duncan mcIlijch

**Achnabrecks lands
in Glassarie paroach****Kilmichell**

John Pullock (2)
 John Stinson
 Allexr Campbell
 Donald Campbell
 Duncan mcIlvernock
 Hew mcOlvea
 Duncan mcCarran
 Donald Roy Campbell
 Donald mcKoin
 Jean Campbell
 Elizabeth Campbell
 More Campbell
 Duncan mcCallum
 Jon McCurie for his house & Smidie (2)

Ballimore

John Stinson elder
 Allexr Stinson
 John Stinson younger

William Stinson
 Do[nal]d Calbreth for house & kilne (2)
 Ard Boyd
 Ane kiln

Gortanrenock

John mcCallum
 Donald mcOlevane
 Duncan Clerk
 Tavish mcCavish
 Duncan mcCallum
 John mcChruttir
 Duncan mcCallum younger
 Duncan mcOlwill

Knock

Allexr Campbell
 John mcArthor
 Gilbert mcIlester

Gallanich

Duncan mcCallum
 Collin Campbell

Ardachastell more

ffinlay mcIntylleor
 Johne mcCurrie
 Duncan mcChrutur
 John Campbell
 Duncan Campbell

Ardachastell beg

William King
 Neill Litch
 John Campbell
 Johne Litch

Monerinich

Allexr Campbell
 Hew mcInlijch [McKinley]
 John mcInun

Dounads lands

Allan mcLauchlan
 John Campbell
 Neill mcffune
 Malcolme mcKeller
 Ane kiln

Barnakill

Donald mcOlbreid
 Angus mcIntylleor
 Ard mcIntylleor
 Allexr mcIntylleor

**Glenans lands in Glaserie
and Kilmartin paroachs**

Lagg
Collin Campbell (2)
Lauchlan mcCavish
John Campbell
Darinanerenich
Malcolm mcInlijch [McKinley]

Collin McLauchlans lands

Two Bravallichs
Donald Monidra
John mcIlvorie
John Roy McKeller
John mcKeller elder
John mcKeller younger
John mcIndoir
Ane kilne
Ardarie
Duncan mckeller
Dougall mcKeller
ffinicharn
Ard mcLauchlan
Duncan mcKeller
Donald mcKeller
John mcNokeard
Dougall mcIlmun
Ane kilne
Ederlinemore
Malcolme mcNokeard
John mcVicare
Ard Campbell

Collin mcLauchlan
Ane kilne
Ederlinebeg
Ard mcArthor for his house and Milne (2)
Ard mcCavish
Duncan mcCalpin
John Munro
Knockalva
John mcCallum
Angus Campbell
Ane kilne

**Ane List of all the hearths
of Craigintyrv[ies] lands in
Glaserie & Kilmartin**

Two Shirwans
Ard mcLauchlan
John Flimeing
Querie Litch
Malcolm mcCalpin
Donald mcLawrtich
Ane kiln
Wper Shirwan
Johne mcCalpin
Duncan Blare
Dougall mcCalpin
Patrick mcArthur
John Litch
Ard Litch
Ane kiln

The number of hearths is one for each householder, unless otherwise specified in brackets. The lands of Campbell of Glenan and McLachlan of Craigentervie in Kilmartin have been omitted. Note that Lamont of Monidrain's lands were Monidrain and Drim only.

Appendix VIII
Fencible Men in Glassary in 1692
and their arms

National Records of Scotland MS. SC54/24/1, pp. 47–54

Bravalichs		Darinerinach	
Donald ban mcInroich	g	Malcolm mcInlish	–
John mcolvory	gs	Auchidaharly	
John Dow mcKellar	2g	Rott : paull	–
John roy mcKellar	gs	Alexr Campbell	–
John mcIndoir	–	Torblaren	
John mcgouin	g	Ard : mcNicoll	
John mcKellar coatter ab : seik		Thomas Dick	–
Louinsachan		Alexr McCavish	–
Alexr : Campbell ab.		Charles mcIllmun	s
Arderie		Duncan mcarthor ab :	
Duncan McKellar	gs	Barchuill	
Dougall mcKellar	gs	Alexr Campbell	s
Over ffincharin		Dougall Campbell	gs
Neill McIndoir		Moninirinaig	
Donald McIndoir		Alexr Campbell	gs
Hew McKellar		Malcolm Campbell	s
William mcRouarij		John mcIllmun	H
Nether ffincharin		Ard Campbell	–
_____ [deserted]		Tunis	
Garvalt		John mcIllevin	gs
Duncan mcThavish	–	Donald mcIllevin	gs
Doug : mcpaull [deleted]		Two Carnans	
Hew mcCallij	gs	Charles McIllmun	–
John mcNeill	s	Hew mcInlich ab :	s
John Campbell in ye Gortan ab. [deleted]		Craiginuir	
Ederling moir		wast	
Malcolm mcNokaird	s	Duppein	
John mcVickar	s	Duncan mcLauchlan	gs
Ard : Campbell	gs	Iver Campbell	gs
Ard mcNokaird	–	Duncan Dow Campbell old	
Ederlingbeg		Craigmuriell	
Ard mcThavish ab : seik	s	John mcInlich	s
Ard : mcarthur	–	John Campbell	p
John mcInroich	s	Wylla	
John mcolvory ab :	–	Ard : Campbell	gs
Lagg		Duncan mcIver	–
Lauchlan mcThavish	g	James Orr	–
John Campbell	–	Donald mcNicoll	gs
Ard Campbell	s	Ballimoir Kilmichell	
Hew mcThavish ab : seik		Alexr Stinson	

John Stinson elder [deleted]		Alexr Campbell	s
John Stinson younger	s	Lauchlan mcThavish ab : seik	
William Stinson	gs	Donald mcCavish old	
Alexr Calbreth	s	Alexr mcThavish	gs
Neill mcIlvernock [deleted]		John mcCarran	–
John Cunningham hird		Dougall Campbell	s
Ard Boyd Leam		Ard : mcVicar	s
Kilmichell		John mcCarran [deleted]	
Duncan mcIlvernock	g	Donald mcThavish	–
John mcWurich		Douincholgin	
Torquill mcNeill	gs	Duncan mcCarran	–
Donald mcEouin		Ard Stewart	–
John Stinson		John mcThavish	s
Donald roy Campbell	gs	Lingartan	
Duncan mcffinden		Colin Campbell ab :	
Donald dow Campbell	g	John Campbell	s
Duncan mcCarran	s	Iver mcBreatnich	s
William Brown	gs	Ballimoir aird	
John Glass		Alexr Cambell	gs
Alexr Campbell	s	John Campbell	s
Auchihoise		Gillies mcIlvernock	–
Alexr mcThavish	gs	John Campbell yor	–
Donald mcThavish	s	Donald mcIlvernock ab :	
Lauchlan mcThavish	g	Kilmichelbeg	
Auchinbreck		Angus mcIlvernock	sH
Alexr mcCavish	–	Rott ferguson	–
Donald mcCavish	g	Hew Black	s
Neill mcInlich	s	John muddie	–
Ard : mcLardich	–	Lauchlan mcThavish	s
Tuo Monidraines		Gilmarnok mcIlvernock	s
Alexr mcTavish	s	Donald mcNokaird	g
Donald mcIlvernock	–	Ardnaherir	
Georg Whyte		wast	
Donald mcNeill	g	Auchinba	
Duncan Lamont	g	Callum Grasich	gs
Donald mcIlglash ab : hird		Hew mcThavish	s
Hew mcTavish ab : at Lochabir		Blairbuy	
Drum		Duncan mcfaill	–
Alexr Stewart	–	John mcfaill	s
John mcIlluij seik ab.		Dougall mcfaill	g
Ard mcVickar	s	Carick	
Alexr mclardich	s	John Mathie	s
Alexr Campbell	g	John mcKerras	–
Wm Stewart	–	Hew mcInlaister	s
Duncan mcIlluij	–	Malcolm mcgrasich	–
ffairnoch		Gallanach	
Wm Whyte ab : old		Duncan mcCallum	gs
Angous Lamount	s	Knock	
John Jonstoun poor		Gilbert mcInlaister [deleted] old	
Kilmorij		Donald mcInlaister	s
Duncan Campbell	s		

Gortanroinich		Dounad	
Donald mcIllevin old		Neill mcphuine	gs
Duncan Clerk	s	Malcolm mcKellar	s
Stephen Whyte	g	John Campbell [deleted] past ye deatt	
Duncan mcCally elder	–	Barnakeill	
Duncan mcCally yo :	–	Angous mcIntaillor	–
John moir mcCally	gs	Donald mcolbreid	gs
Colin Campbell	gs	Alexr mcIntaillor	–
Donald mcIllevin yo :	s	Neill mcThavish	g
Ardcastlemoir & Airdchastlebeg		John mcVickar seik	
William King	–	Dunemuck	
Charles Campbell	g	Dougall Campbell	gs
Duncan Campbell	s	Charles Campbell	gs
Neill mcInlich	gs	Alan mcLauchlan	gs
John mcWurich	gs	Ronald mcLauchlan	s
Alexr mcWurich ab : at ye Loulands		Dugall mceffinden	gs
Kilmichelbeg		Neill mcolvory	s
Duncan Campbell	–	Lauchlan mcLauchlan	gs
Kenneth mcCarran	–	John mcInlich	
Patt : mcThavish	–	Alexr mcLardich	–
John Craford	–	Achinschelach	
Tavish mcMartin	–	Lauchlan mcLauchlan	gs
John mcIlvaine	–	Georg Stinson	s
Minart		Duncan mcInlich ab :	–
John mcNokaird	–	Doukirnan	
Duncan mcIlvain	–	Gilbert mcLauchlan	s
Gilchrist mcMartin	–	John Orr	s
John mcNouccater	g	Over Kames	
John mcCoill	s	John mcLauchlan	s
Over Shervin		Lauchlan mcLauchlan elder	gs
John mcInlich	gs	Lauchlan mcLauchlan yor	–
Patt : mearthur	s	Malcolm mcIlvernock	g
Dougall mcalpin	gs	Nethir Keames	
Duncan mcVorisht	–	Ard : Campbell	s
Midle Shervin		Angous mcEouin	s
John Burn	s	Duncan mcChruter	g
Donald mcLardich	–	John Stinsone	g
Ard mcLardich	s	Drainlia	
Duncan mcInlich	–	John mcBrain	g
John ffleiming	–	John mcLauchlan a hird	
Malcom mcIntailor	–	Gortangour	
John mcVorlich	g	Ard mcNicoll ffewar	
Kallinochinach		Andrew Muray	s
Donald ban mcphuine	s	Neill mcIntaillor	s
Donald mcCally	–	Duncan mcNokaird	g
Duncan mcBraine	–	Gallanach	
Donald mcLauchlan	–	Dougall mcIlvaird	gs
Dougall mcInlaister	–	Wm McNicoll	gs
Callum mcCally	s	Brainchaillis	
		Neill mcVickar	s

Angous mcNicoll	gs	ffairnoch	
Duncan mcIlchattan	g	Charles mcIllmun yrof	
Darinloch		Donald mcIllmun yr	s
Angous Campbell	–	Kirnanmoir	
Leckvory		Wm pollick	gs
Angous mcIllmun	–	Alexr Campbell	s
Alexr mcolvae	–	Lauchlan mcPhaiden	sH
Ard Campbell	s	John Paull	–
John mcIllmun seek ab:		Donald Mcbrain	–
Ovir ffincharin [repeated]		Malcolm mcolva	–
Neill mcIndoir	gs	Kirnanbeg	
Donald mcIndoir ab :		John mcChruter	gs
Hew mcKellar ab :		Hew roy Campbell	gs
Wm : mcgoun ab :		Donald roy Campbell ab :	
Nethir ffincharin & Kilnuir		Auchilak	
Donald ban mcCaill yr	s	Angous Campbell	gs
Duncan mcKaill	g	Auchidrom	
Ard mcLauchlan	s	John mcKellar	s
John mcNokaird	s	Keneth mcNicoll	s
John mcNokaird yor	s	John mcalpin	gs
Hew Campbell	–	Karnaim	
Duncan mcIllevin	–	Lauchlan mcLauchlan	gs
Nethir ffincharin		Knockalva	
Dougall mcIllmun	gs	Neill mcInlich	s
Glesvar		ffoirling	
Jo : mcCavish	–	Dugall mcGrigor ab :	
Alexr mcIver	–	Donald mcInlaister ab : seik	
Hew Glass ab :		Stronalbanach	
Iver Campbell yr	p	Alexr Lamount fier yrof.	
Donald mcMha	–	Donald mcThavish	s
Gilbert mcalpin ab :		Malcolm mcNokaird	s
Malcolm mcguriman	–	Crarae	
Barmolach		Ard Campbell	
John mcClulich	–	Jo : mcIlmaluag	gs
Duncan mcIlvory	–	Neill mcCavish	s
Patt : mcIllevin seik : ab		Donald Craford	–
Angous mcIllmun	–	Duncan Campbell	–
Gilbert Black	–	Gilbert mcblaren	s
Duncan mcLaurin	–	Garvachie	
Eorkoch		Alexr mcThavish	
Duncan mcIllmun portioner	gs	John mcInlaister	
Dugall mcIllmun portioner	gs	John mcIlchattan	
John Car ab :		Inverhea	
Gilmartin mcNokaird ab.		John mcIllevin	–
Leattirnamolt		Rory mcCavish	–
Malcolm mcolvae	–	Jo : bane mcIlpadrick	gs
Alexr Campbell	s	Neill mcCavish	gs
Kandlochlean		Auchigyll	
Alexr mcIllmun	s	John mcInturnor	gs
Charles Campbell	gs	Donald mcInturnor	gs
John Campbell	–	Alexr Craford	gs

Stronaisker		Nethir Roudill	
Donald mcCally	gsH	Lauchlan mcNouccatter	—
Duncan mcCally	s	Donald mcgoun	—
Ard mcChruter	s	Gilbert mcNeill	—
Donald mcNeill	s	Ard : mcblaren	—
Dugald Clerk	—	Knocknakeill	
Baryll		Alexr mcarthor	g
Neill Campbell	gs	Duncan mcGalloglich	s
Over Roudill		Kilbryde	
Patt : Campbell ab :		Ard mcInlich	gs
John Campbell ab :			
Donald mcIlphadrick	—		

This list of men aged between 16 and 60 years, judged suitable to serve in the national army ('fencible men'), was drawn up by Archibald McLachlan of Craigentervie and Alan McLachlan of Dunad, and submitted on 16 May 1692. The arms possessed by the men are indicated as follows: g = gun, s = sword, p = pistol, H = halberd, — = no arms, blank = no return.

Appendix IX

Glassary delinquents in 1709

National Records of Scotland MS. SC54/17/2/34/10

Stroneskir

- Gilbert Black
- Alexr Campbell
- Archd Campbell
- Malcolm Campbell

Glasvar

- Angus Campbell of Glasvar
- Charles Campbell tutor of Glasvar
- John Thomson
- Alexr Campbell

Barmolloch

- Malcolm Campbell of Barmolloch
- Patrick mcIllevin
 - Alexr Campbell

Upper Rudall

- Ard Campbell
- Dug mcIlmichael

Kilbryd

- Lachlan mcLachlan
- John Pearson?
- Lachlan Campbell

Baroile

- Dugald Campbell

Nethir Rudele

John mcArthur

Upper Shirvanie

- Neil mcCallum
John mcKellar
- Neil Campbell maltman

Midle Shirvanie

Alexr mcLachlan miller

Killinochenach

Kenneth mcLachlan heritor

- Neill Leich
- Malcolm mcCallum maltman

Dunad

- Arch mcBlaren
- John mcDugald
- James Boyd
- Allan mcLachlan of Dunad
- Archd Campbell herd

Barnakeile

Donald mcLachlan fiar of Dunad
Donald mcBrien
John Campbell

Dunnamuck

- Donald mcBrayen miller
- Neil ban mcPhun

Auchinshelloch

- Allan mcLachlan
- John Leich formerly in auchadagherlich

Toreblaren

- Duncan Campbell
- John mcMartin yr in auchadagherlich

Lagg

- John mcIllevin formerly in upper rudell
- Angus Campbell

Leckguarij

- John Campbell feur of Leckguary
- Alexr Campbell
- Malcolm Campbell
- Archd McKellar

Kirnan

- Archibald Stevinson
- John Barr miller

Sockoch

- Donald mcLachlan
- John mcIlghairun formerly in
Dunnamuck

Over Bravellich

- Andrew Carswell

Nether Bravellich

- John mcKellar
- Ellar McKellar
- Donald ban mcLellan
- Donald McKellar
- Archd McKellar

Upper fincharn

- Duncan mcIlevin
- Donald mcIndoar

Nether fincharn

- Archd mcLachlan
- John mcNokard
- Donald Campbell

- John Leich
- Donald mcKellar
- Alexr Campbell

Edderlinebeg

- Neil mcNicoll miller

Garvalt

- George Paull
- John Campbell formerly in Stroneskur

Creginewir

- Duncan mcKellar

Lochgerr

- James Pollich formerly in Kilmichell

Kilmichell

- Donald Campbell
- Gorry Stevinson
- James Galbeath
- James Stevinson

The names of men found guilty are preceded by a bullet.

Appendix X

Glassary 1750 valuation

National Records of Scotland, MS. SC51/59/1, Land Tax rolls for Argyll, vol. 1, pp. 31–35.

Colin Campbell of Ederline

Two Ederlines & Crofts	6m/£12.10.7
Corn Mill thereof	—/£1. 7. 7
Garvalt	3m/£6. 19. 0
Nether Fincharn	6m/£11. 1. 1
Upper Fincharn	4m/£ 8. 5.6
Nether Braveallich	2½m/£ 8.13.1
Upper Braveallich	2½m/£ 8.13.1
Soccoch	3m/£ 4. 7. 2
Cregnewr	2m/£ 4. 3. 4
Feorline	3m/£10. 6. 8
Garvachie	2m/£ 4.13. 3
Inverea	2½m/£ 5. 3.10
Crarae & Acre	2½m/£ 5. 7. 9
Gallanich	¾m/£ 3. 6. 8
Dryenlia	2m/£ 1.15. 6
Gortenaour	3m/£ 5. 8. 4
Nether Brenchelly	2½m/£ 7. 9.10
Upper Brenchelly	2½m/£ 8. 5.10

Archd. McCallum of Poltalloch

Knockalaway	2½m/£ 7. 0. 6
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Archd. Campbell of Knockbuy

Minard, inc. Shirghrims, Knockbuy & the Mill	6m/£22.12.11
Kilmichelbeg	5m/£11. 8. 4
Achaghoyll	2½m/£ 7.15.0
Barchuill	2m/£ 5. 0. 0
Tunns	2m/£ 7.10.0
Over Carran	1m/£ 3. 0. 6
Torblaren	3m/£ 6. 0. 0
Monyniarnich	3m/£10.17. 2

Sir James Campbell of Auchinbreck

Kilmichell in Glasrie	3m/£ 6.13. 4
Kilmichell, tenements	—/£ 6. 3. 0
Acres annexed	—/£ 1. 2. 6

Ballimore Kilmichell

Acres & Corn Mill	7m/£29.16. 6
Ardechastels & New farm	5m/£17.10. 0
Gortennannich, Black Park Acre, etc.	5m/£14.15. 0
Corn Mill thereof	—/£ 1. 2. 7
Knock & pendicles	4m/£12.10. 0
Derinloch	—/£ 3. 0. 0
Gallanoch: Loch Ger	1m/£ 5. 0. 0
Upper Kaimes & Tayinrow	2½m/£10. 3. 4
Nether Kaimes	2½m/£ 5. 5. 0
Carrick	3m/£ 11. 2. 8
Ferrier's possessions	—/£ 2. 0. 0
Blarebuy	2½m/£ 4. 3. 4
Duppine	3m/£ 8. 6. 8
Ardnaherrir	2½m/£ 7.10. 0
Achnabaw	2m/£ 7. 0. 0
Ballimore Aird & Mill Acre	3m/£12. 2. 6
Silvercraigs Corn Mill	—/£ 1.10. 2
Kilmichelbeg & Castletown	3m/£12. 3. 4
Drim & Acres	3m/£ 8. 6. 8
Corn Mill thereof	—/£ 2. 1. 1
Fernoch	2m/£ 9. 7. 2
Achenbreck	2m/£ 8. 6. 8
Salmon fishing Water of Add	—/£ 1. 0. 0

Patrick Campbell, wadsetter

Linghartan	2½m/£ 6.15. 0
Duncholgin	2½m/£ 6.15. 0

John Campbell

Kilmorry	3m/£10. 6. 4
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Call. Lamont

Monydryens	4m/£13. 0.10
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Dugald McTavish of Dunardary
Auchachoish 3m/£11. 6. 1

Duncan McLachlan of Dunadd
Barnakill 2m/£ 6. 7. 2
Dunadd 3m/£13. 3. 4
Tayinlluick Corn Mill —/£ 2. 6. 0

Kenneth McLachlan
Killenochanoch 2m/£10. 0. 0

Alexr. Campbell of Shirvane
Dunnimuck 5m/£16. 3. 8
Achinsheloch 5m/£ 8. 8. 2
Achinsheloch Acre —/£ 2. 5. 6
Corn Mill thereof —/£ 2. 0. 0
Bareyle & Acre 4m/£ 5. 5.11
Upper Shirvane 3½m/£12. 5. 5
Nether Rudil 4m/£ 7. 3.10
Middle Shirvane —/£14. 6. 3

James Campbell of Rudil
Over Rudil
& Taynabenny 3m/£ 7.11. 1
Kilbryde 1½m/£ 3. 1. 7
& half Knocknaheilt

Colin McLachlan
Achiyerran & Carnaim 3½m/£ 6. 8.10
Ardary 2m/£ 3. 6. 8

Donald Campbell
Stroneskir 3m/£13. 5.10

Charles Campbell
Barmolloch 5m/£12. 2. 0

James Campbell
Glasvar 4½m/£12. 5. 6

Patrick McKellar
Stronalbanach 2m/£ 7. 5. 0
Lettirmolt 2m/£ 5.16. 1

Malcolm Campbell
Leckuary 3m/£ 7. 05. 8

Duncan Campbell of Kirnan
Two Kirnans 4m/£10. 6. 8
Achadaherlich 1½m/£ 4. 4. 5
Lagg 3m/£ 6.13. 4
Derinernach 1½m/£ 3. 1. 1
& Derinakerdoch
Fernoch: Lochlean 1½m/£ 3. 0. 0
Nether Carran 1m/£ 2.10. 0
Kenlochlean 1½m/£ 3. 6. 8
Auchalik 1m/£ 3. 3.10

Duncan Campbell of Duchernan
Uila 3m/£ 5.16. 0
Cregmurrell 2m/£ 3.15. 0
Duchernan 1½m/£ 2.15. 0

Land values are in merklands (m) and assessed rentals in pounds sterling (£), shillings and pence.